

THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NEOPHYTE NON-INDIGENOUS ELEMENTARY TEACHERS TEACHING IN IP SCHOOLS

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The Lived Experiences of Neophyte Non-Indigenous Elementary Teachers Teaching in IP Schools

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers who graduated from elementary education-generalist program. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating fourteen neophyte non-indigenous teachers from Davao del Norte teaching in IP schools. All of them participated in the in-depth interview. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: Facing Difficulties Due to language barriers in the teaching environment, struggling to Educate Indigenous students amidst language barriers and diverse academic abilities, Prioritizing cultural understanding and respect for diverse learning styles, and contextualizing student's culture and surroundings. They deemed the following coping strategies essential: Embracing flexibility to understand and communicate effectively within their language culture, seeking support from stakeholders for guidance and insights, conducting Home visits to understand IP student's behavior and circumstance's, and managing student's behaviors within guidance from colleagues. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: Effective instruction results in positive students' performance, Emphasize Technologies Vital Role in Education For improved Learning and Digital Literacy, Offer teachers Trainings on Culturally responsive teaching for Indigenous students, Teaching Indigenous students Requires Cultural Understanding and adaptability, The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

New non-Indigenous elementary teachers play a key role in shaping the education and future of Indigenous students, but their experiences in teaching Indigenous communities are often overlooked in mainstream education discussions. Teaching Indigenous learners can be difficult, especially for new non-Indigenous teachers who may lack the experience and knowledge of effective teaching strategies. Many of these teachers are unprepared for the challenges they face in the classroom. To provide equal educational opportunities for all students, teachers need to be culturally aware and knowledgeable about different cultures (Banks & Banks, 2020). Their teaching methods have a direct impact on students' attitudes toward learning and their academic success (Hu et al., 2018).

In China, Native-English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) and Non-Native- English-Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) both face challenges related to language barriers. NESTs have strong cultural knowledge of English-speaking countries but are often unfamiliar with local culture and education systems. In contrast, NNESTs understand the local students, education policies, and exams, but may not know as much about English-speaking cultures. In terms of teaching styles, NESTs usually focus on activities that help students communicate, while NNESTs often concentrate more on explaining grammar and language details (Rao & Chen, 2019). Additionally, while NESTs are fluent in English, they don't have experience learning it as a second language and may not understand or speak the students' native language. This can make it harder for them to connect with students' learning needs (Sarigül, 2018). On the other hand, NNESTs have the advantage of having learned English as a foreign language themselves, which helps shape their teaching strategies (Novianti, 2018). Still, having native speakers in a school often attracts attention, as it suggests a higher level of education.

In the Philippines, particular in Cabuyao Integrated High School in Laguna, Philippines, improving teaching strategies comes with many challenges that make it hard for indigenous students to learn a new language (Leaño et al., 2019). Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) teachers still find it difficult to apply certain teaching methods to language instruction because of the different needs of these learners (Protacio, 2021). The curriculum aims to make students skilled in the Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English, which helps them understand various forms of communication in today's globalized world (Barrot, 2018).

The researcher planned to conduct the study because it will be highly important to society. This study is urgently needed since it will help new, non-indigenous elementary teachers understand the various methods and strategies for teaching schools for the indigenous people. Ignoring the issues would have resulted in a loss of opportunity to raise the standard of education for indigenous students, a chance to continue using bad teaching methods, and insufficient support networks. The researcher it will important to pursue this study because it could have inform educational system. Enhance the quality of indigenous pupil learners, their instructional practices, promoted educational equity, and contributed to the professional growth and retention of teachers. Ultimately, this study outcomes had the potential to positively impact the overall the lived experiences elementary non- indigenous teachers.

In connection, related studies had been found regarding the phenomenon of the difficulties teaching indigenous health entitled: "We still have a lot to learn": non- Indigenous educator perspectives on teaching Indigenous health" The study by Francis-Cracknell et al. (2022) highlights the need for educators to strengthen their understanding of effective teaching methods, the effects of settler

colonialism, and how to challenge colonial patterns in education. The findings suggest that unless schools move away from colonial practices and embrace cultural safety in teaching, efforts to improve health equity for Aboriginal communities will remain inadequate. However, the uniqueness of the current study laid in its specific focus on the lived experience of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers in their instructional strategies to overcome language barrier among IPs learner, who were teaching in indigenous people schools. The study conducted interviews with the neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers to gain valuable insights into their specific challenges and experiences.

Research Questions

This study aimed to the specific experiences of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers teaching in indigenous people schools. Research questions that guided this Qualitative study were the following:

1. What are the lived experiences encountered by neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers handling indigenous pupil learners?
2. What are the coping strategies of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers handling indigenous pupil learners?
3. What are the insights can neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers share to the academe?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research design, which aims to understand the nature of a situation and the experiences of people in that context. The study followed a phenomenological approach, which focuses on exploring and understanding the experiences of non-Indigenous teachers. The goal of this qualitative study is to answer the research question from a broad, idealistic perspective, looking at people's attitudes, behaviors, interactions, and beliefs. Qualitative methods are used to gather non- numerical data, such as words and language. Researchers from various fields are increasingly interested in using qualitative research in intervention studies (Pathak et al, 2013).

The study used thematic analysis to examine, organize, and test the collected data. According to Gibson and Brown (2009), thematic analysis involves looking for common elements, differences, and relationships in the data. Most of the data was coded, and after classifying and comparing the differences, the main topics that answered the research questions were identified. The purpose of the thematic analysis was to find patterns, or themes, in important or interesting data and use these themes to address the research problems. The R Analytical Tool, an open-source statistical software, was also used for the analysis (Gibson & Brown, 2009).

In addition, quantitative descriptive designs were used to explain the responses to strategies, trends, methods, and teaching techniques in the context of the "new normal" learning environment for students. It also discusses the quantitative research design, including the methods, structures, and factors that influenced the study's findings. This helps in understanding the research process and design (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

Participants

This study utilized a research design that is qualitative-phenomenological in nature. It is for the purpose of ascertaining the views of experiences of neophyte non- indigenous elementary teacher on their perspective to teaching in indigenous people schools. The studies data come from participants' answers during interviews, based on a set of guided questions. It also includes the stories and experiences they shared. The study assumes that participants were honest and accurate in their responses, and their behavior was also observed during the interviews.

In this phenomenological study, the participants are professional neophyte indigenous elementary teachers teaching indigenous people schools. Also, the criteria established by the researcher are suitable for the study. The participants were selected based on the following criteria: (1) non-indigenous elementary teachers. (2) Teaching for a minimum of (6) six months to (1) one year (3) teaching indigenous pupil learners. The number of participants will a total of fourteen (14) participants underwent interview (IDI). Phenomenological research is typically conducted through the use of in-depth interview, are a way to elicit deeper understanding of a topic or concept or to elicit more detailed information (Kvale, 1996).

The researcher utilized the purposive sampling method in recruiting the 14 participants for the study. A deliberate selection of an informant based on the qualities the informant possesses is the purposive sampling technique, also known as judgment sampling. It is a non- random technique that does not call for a predetermined number of informants or underlying theories, sampling put, the researcher decides what information is necessary to have and then goes out looking for people who can and are willing to share it due to their knowledge or experience (Bernard, 2002).

Moreover, the researcher recognizes the limitations of the study, acknowledging that it may not fully capture the complete picture. Because only a small number of participants were involved, the findings cannot be generalized beyond this specific group. While small sample sizes are common in qualitative research, they are not always enough to support strong conclusions. Mason (2002) also notes that a case study requires extended engagement and regular contact with participants, but due to the researcher's professional

commitments, time constraints may have affected the study's credibility (Mason, 2002).

Procedure

First, prior to conducting the study, an approval letter from the college president of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology were sent to the Office of the vice Presidents for Academic Affairs, and specifically to the institution concerned. Obtained and noted by research consultant. The used of forms for date collection, as recommended in the phenomenological research inquiry, was carried out. A guide questionnaire were employed. The interview question are presented first to the panel of examiners for approval to be able to proceed to the next step of date collection.

Second, the data are first converted form the original language to Standard English by the researcher after it had been recorded. The research was conducted after date had been translated, and using the thematic analysis tenets, the researcher extracted the emerging themes. Finally, the themes that had been extracted are given to a data analyst whose knowledge of language research are compatible for approval and verification (Creswell, 2013).

Third, after approval, information about the study's significance, purpose, and goal were provided to participants and individuals. Depending on which language the participants spoke best, each question on the interview guide are translated. In addition, participants could respond to the questions in whichever language they felt most at ease.

Fourth, an informed consent form detailing the participants' voluntary participation in the study is given to them to sign. Next it is critical for the researcher to explain to the participants how their privacy were protected. This means that the information was only used for the study. For the conducted of in-in-depth interview and focus group discussion, as schedule was established.

Moreover, the researcher before the interview started, the researcher thanked the participants for their time and willingness to share. The researcher then explained the purpose of the study and let them know that the interview would be recorded, but their faces would be blurred to protect their identities.

In addition, the researcher prepared questions in advance of the scheduled time for the focus discussion and in-depth interview, and these question are approved by the experts. The researcher separately conducted our IDI with fourteen (14) participants. It were noted too asked for their consent and permission before starting to record the interviews.

Then, the researcher started to glean the experience of the participants. Each question on the interview guide will translated into any language that the participants understand best. Furthermore, the question are answered in any language the participation is most comfortable with.

Moving on from the data transcription, the participants and informants are called to sign their certificates of completion as the participants of the study. Lastly, as a sign of thanks, tokens are given to the participants who wholeheartedly expressed their feeling and emotion, as well as their valued time and effort in this study.

Data Analysis

Data analysis for this phenomenological study used the descriptive phenomenological method. A specific phenomenon is meant to be describe as a lived experience through the study of phenomena. A person perception of a particular phenomenon is given meaning by lived experience of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers, which present the experiences reality in the person life. According to Smith and Osborn (2015), the phenomenological analysis aim to shed light on the phenomenon's core. Additionally, the descriptive phenomenological approach were appropriate for examining the teacher's subjective perceptions of their lived experience of elementary non-indigenous teachers. The phenomenological analysis aim to shed light on the phenomenon's core, additionally the descriptive phenomenological approach will appropriate for examining the neophyte indigenous elementary teachers' subjective perceptions of their participation in online trainings and webinars under the new normal.

In my study, the gathered data in this research will displayed and analyzed based on the needs and objectives of this research endeavor. In addition, the interviews of participants would be transcribed, and essential quotes would be highlighted. Researchers went over each study participant's data to obtain a feel of the overall picture, writing notes and codes in the margins to identify potentially significant markers of the experience. This process is called "horizontalization" in the assumption that all components of a description are related to one another and that understanding the relationship between the parts requires reading the complete description at least once.

As such, Lune and Berg (2017) defined data analysis in qualitative studies as the process of methodically searching and organizing interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual materials. The purpose of this process will be to help the researcher gather information and deepen the public's understanding of the phenomenon or research topic.

In addition, the transcripts of the selected teachers in IDI proceedings have become the main subject for data analysis. The data had undergone various treatments and processes to extract the findings of the study. Finally, researchers look through the altered meaning units for patterns and essential elements, which are synthesized into a textual experience structure.

Furthermore, in this study, thematic analysis was used, which is the process of finding, analyzing, and presenting patterns in large amounts of data. It helps uncover detailed and rich descriptions from the study's results (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). Thematic analysis

was helpful because it allows the analysis of qualitative data to understand people's views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or values (Caulfield, 2019).

Hence, the steps researchers follow in data analysis include getting familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, evaluating those themes, defining and naming the themes, and finally, writing the report. Data reduction is also part of the process, which involves removing unnecessary data and turning the useful data into something valuable for the study. This technique ensures the data remains accurate while reducing its volume, to help with this, a data analyst was brought in to assist the researchers in combining, managing, sorting, and organizing the data more effectively (Neha, 2020).

Ethical Considerations

When collecting data from people, scientists and researchers must follow ethical rules that guide how they design and carry out their studies. The goal of human research is often to understand real-life events, find effective treatments, study behavior, and improve lives in various ways. It is important to follow ethical guidelines in research to maintain trustworthiness, improve the quality of the study, and protect the rights of the participants (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for persons were an ethical principle that emphasizes consideration for other people and acknowledges their inherent autonomy. By giving participants enough information about the nature and purpose of this research study in the participant's information leaflet in a comprehensible way to improve their informed consent, the concept of autonomy can be upheld (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

In this study, an informed consent form was created in advance for the participants. The form provided detailed information about the study, allowing interested individuals to learn more about it. During the interviews, the researcher respected the opinions and perspectives of the participants. It was crucial to establish a respectful relationship with the participants, considering their viewpoints, culture, and way of life, and giving them the choice to participate or not. The participants are always respected, as their importance were prioritized over the study. Before each interview, the researcher sought permission to record the entire conversation and the participants' responses. Additionally, the participants are informed of their rights to be informed about the study results.

Consent were formalized in order to protect people's right to choose whether or not to engage in the research, and to foster research interactions that is built on "trust and integrity." It is crucial that a person's decision to participate in the research will voluntary and based on accurate knowledge about the implications of their involvement (Klykken, 2021). Ensuring the validity of consent was a fundamental requirement in the past.

In this study, the participants are encouraged to make informed choices and voluntarily participate, adhering to ethical research standards. They were informed of their rights, including the right to ask questions during the interview, the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and the right to leave the interview without providing an explanation. If a participant chose to leave in the middle of the interview, the researcher respected their decision. The researcher ensured that every participants are enthusiastic and motivated to contribute to the success of the study. During the interviews, the researcher obtained consent to record the entire conversation to capture a comprehensive understanding of their experiences.

Benevolence it highlights that the study should benefit the participants, not put them at risk. The focus is on reducing risks to participants rather than making a profit from them. To keep participants safe, their identities were kept anonymous. At all times, their information was protected, and no data was left unsecured or unattended (Kirsh, 2019).

The researcher secured a safe location for conducting face-to-face interviews, prioritizing the safety of all participants. During the interviews, participants are provided a secure environment where they could freely share their stories without fear of rejection or criticism. To mitigate psychological risks, the information gathered during the interviews will kept confidential and secure, minimizing the potential for negative outcomes such as shame or embarrassment.

Confidentiality the focus is on the research findings and making sure participants are safe. The identities of the participants are kept secret. After the data is analyzed, all materials like videos, transcripts, notes, and others will be destroyed. Some participants were initially nervous about the interview because they weren't sure what to say, but once the researcher assured them that their responses would be confidential, they felt more comfortable answering the questions. The researcher was careful with the questions, and the study was handled with respect.

The researcher made sure that each participant were identified using discrete coding. This provision is based on Republic Act 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which specifies that any information that could be used to identify participants by name, gender, ethnicity, or occupation should be appropriately written to protect participant anonymity. As a result, suitable coding and other safeguards were implemented to secure the participants' identities. In addition, none of my research participants are ever obliged to provide their names on any of the study's forms. The researcher also conducted a firsthand transcription of the interviews. Research data shall be stored and be destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Justice this means that everyone involved in the study should be treated fairly. In my case, the researcher made sure the participants were chosen fairly using a purposive sampling method. This method ensures that risks and benefits are shared fairly as part of the research process.

To ensure justice, the participants are not required to spend any money as their contribution to the research were acknowledged. The researcher recognized the importance of all participants and credited them for their valuable contributions to the study. Their efforts was fully appreciated, and as a gesture of gratitude, practical tokens are provided to express appreciation for their involvement in the research.

Results and Discussion

This section was split into two parts: Part one explained the steps of analyzing the data and organizing the main themes that came from the in-depth interviews. Part two provided a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of the study were the neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers who were a graduate of Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist from in Langilan District and public schools. They were all non-indigenous elementary teachers who were teaching for almost six months (6) and one year services. There were total of fourteen (14) non-indigenous elementary teachers involved in the study: three (3) males and eleven (11) females.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Code</i>
Miss behave	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-01
Talker	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-02
Lover	Teacher	27	Female	IDI-03
Madasig	Teacher	28	Female	IDI-04
Mr. Chinito	Teacher	26	Male	IDI-05
Morina	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-06
Mr. Smile	Teacher	26	Male	IDI-07
Disciple	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-08
Alive	Teacher	26	Female	IDI-09
Cutie	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-10
Amore	Teacher	25	Female	IDI-11
Great	Teacher	26	Female	IDI-12
Mr. Gwapo	Teacher	26	Male	IDI-13
Melody	Teacher	28	Female	IDI-14
Total =14				

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face inside the campus of school via audio recording. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. The researcher got what he wanted, and both the Interviewer and the interviewee were pleased with the result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required.

The participants were given the choice to refuse to respond to any question they considered unbeneficial or in opposition to their wishes. To ensure confidentiality, the information or data collected during the interviews was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its nature.

In order to adhere to the data collection process, the researcher used smartphones to record the participants' responses during the interview.

Additionally, the researcher requested permission from all the participants to record the entire conversation during the interview, and they all politely agreed. All participants were accommodating and comprehended the request, except for one condition: that their identities remain anonymous in the study.

All participants in each case were given pseudonym in order to protect the identities of all the participants. Pseudonyms were also given to each participant to protect their identities as well. For instance, Miss Behave was named after the participant who was shine person, while Talker was the name to the participant who always sharing with a past experiences during the interview. Lover was the given named of the participant who had really love her indigenous students as well, while the Madasig was the given named of the participant who had convincing power their students. Mr. Chinito was the given named of the participant who was really cutie eyes. While Morina was the given named of the participant who has really pretty person. Disciple was the given named of the participant who had amazing power to integrate word of God to young children students, while Alive was the given of the participant who was the person is very energetic and alive person. Cutie was the given named of the participant who as very nice and approachable person, Amore was given named of the participant who has loving to the IP school. While Great was given named of the participant who was very a grateful person, Mr. Gwapo was given named of the participants who was attractive, lastly, Melody was given named of the participant who has sweet of communication during the interview

Categorization of the Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

To classify the data, key themes were assigned to each study question. To provide a comprehensive summary, the study's issues were thoroughly discussed and extended to create a vivid presentation. Then came the conclusion and verification, which is the stage of the inquiry when the basic conceptions and patterns surrounding the findings are established (Miles & Huberman 1994).

To improve the study's trustworthiness, the researcher considered the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and conform ability. To address believability, member verification was performed in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants has yet expressed criticism of the transcript or provided contradicting information. They all signed the participant verification form. They said yes. The study's triangulation was possible since it featured readings from participants and related works, or more than two sources (Creswell & Miller, 2000).

To ensure dependability and confirm ability, the researcher included an audit trail. This trail was constructed to allow the research review panel to validate the study's findings, assumptions, and hypotheses (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher declared from the start that the findings could not be generalized because they were based solely on the individuals' personal experiences in the specified locations. Nonetheless, the researchers concluded that when the credibility, confirm ability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are secured, transferability is also addressed (Klein & Myers, 2009).

Research Question 1: What are the lived experiences encountered by neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers handling indigenous pupil learners?

This question sought to investigate and comprehend the firsthand experiences of neophyte or beginner non-indigenous elementary teachers where in teaching IP schools community. It aimed to expose these teachers' struggles, accomplishments, and overall journey as they navigated their first years in the profession. The researcher identified five main themes from the responses of the two individuals. The following themes were: Facing Difficulties Due to Language Barriers in the Teaching Environment, Struggling to Educate Indigenous Students Amidst Language Barriers and Academic Abilities, Prioritizing Cultural Understanding and Respect for Diverse Learning Styles, and Contextualizing Lessons Relevant to the Students Culture and surroundings.

Facing Difficulties Due to Language Barriers in the Teaching Environment

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers the language barriers can present significant challenges in the teaching environment, particularly for teaching indigenous students in hinterland areas schools. These teachers, often new to the profession and the cultural environment, are tasked with not only teaching a curriculum but also bridging a linguistic gap between themselves and their students. Language is the primary medium through which knowledge is transmitted.

Therefore, a lack of proficiency in the local language can hinder the teacher's ability to effectively communicate and impart knowledge. This can lead to misunderstandings and misconceptions, which may negatively impact the students' learning outcomes. Moreover, language barriers can also affect a teacher's ability to engage with the wider school community, including other staff and parents. This can lead to feelings of isolation and hinder their ability to fully integrate into the school environment. The highlighting the significance of these early encounters in shaping the confidence and capabilities of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers.

Table 2. *Experiences of Neophyte Non-indigenous Elementary Teachers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Facing Difficulties Due to Language Barriers in the Teaching Environment	In my experience, learners have their own language when it comes to delivering a lesson. How do you teach a lesson to a child who understands Bisaya, Tagalog, and English? It is really hard when they only know one language. Their language really matters. IDI-03 In my experience, new teachers teaching indigenous students, especially IP learners, find it really hard because of the language barrier. They speak a different language, especially for me when teaching grade 1 and 2 students. They are still young and are more used to speaking in their own language. IDI -11 Based on my experience teaching here, I had a hard time communicating with the children because we speak different languages. We could not understand each other, and that was one of my first experiences teaching here. IDI-09
Struggling to Educate Indigenous Students Amidst Language Barriers and Diverse Academic Abilities	The difficult part of teaching indigenous children is, as I mentioned, it is really hard to teach because the children's learning capacity is low, especially in English subjects. They struggle with Filipino, so even more with English. It becomes very challenging for us as teachers. For me, as a teacher, if they find it hard to understand Bisaya, and even Filipino, it's much harder when it comes to English. IDI-07 Sir, there are times when it is really difficult because out of 28 students, only three can keep up with the

	<p>lesson due to their own language. That's my challenge how to deal with the others who are slower learners. IDI-08</p> <p>I had to make big adjustments because I used to teach in a private school where the learners were very fast. Here in the IP school, I'm really adjusting because the students are slow learners, and I'm also teaching multi-grade, which makes it harder. It is especially difficult for me because I'm not fluent in their language. So, this school year has been all about adjusting for me. IDI-09</p>
<p>Prioritizing Cultural Understanding and Respect for Diverse Learning Styles</p>	<p>It is difficult and challenging, but fulfilling, I give my time by prioritizing my understanding of their culture. I strive to understand the cultural background of my students, who may have different learning styles, communication preferences, and views on education. I also actively engage in professional development to improve my teaching methods. IDI- 14</p> <p>What I do is explain to the children that we have different cultures, so we should respect each other. They understand that we need to be respectful. For example, if I don't understand something or if they don't understand, I make sure to translate it. IDI-03</p> <p>You need to create a peaceful environment where they feel that you are open to accepting their culture and that you respect them. It is important to show respect, love, and peace, and to teach without bias. You should teach the children, especially IP students, properly and fairly. IDI-12</p>
<p>Contextualizing Lessons Relevant to the Students Culture and Surroundings</p>	<p>We need to make lessons relevant to their lives. For example, if I give an activity related to the five senses, like tasting, I do not just use abstract examples. I bring real materials that they can see and use at home. For instance, if we're talking about tastes, I might bring sugar and bitter melon as examples. IDI-03</p> <p>When it comes to integrating IP culture, we try to make our lessons as localized as possible. Although the curriculum is general and covers everything across the division, we adapt it for our classroom by using examples that are relevant to the students' surroundings. IDI-06</p> <p>When integrating indigenous culture, you need to use examples that fit their context. For example, when delivering a lesson, use examples that they can see or find in their own environment. This helps them understand what you are trying to teach more easily. IDI-11</p>

Lover, (pseudonym) candidly shared his struggles with low of confidence of teaching among indigenous students to imparting knowledge them, particularly in IP school. Since language of learners can really overlap communication both teachers and students, in fact the reason of difficult of deliver the lessons.

“So my experiences there a language of the learners when it comes how to deliver there a lesson, how to deliver the lesson nga, unsaon nimo siya pag kanang pagkahibawo na unsaon pagdeliver sa bata nga kabalo sa bisaya, tagalog ug English ang ilaha mn jung, lisod kaayu kuan ang ilang language na nahibaw-an isa rah jud. Ilahang language jud”. (IDI-03)

(In my experience, learners have their own language when it comes to delivering a lesson. How do you teach a lesson to a child who understands Bisaya, Tagalog, and English? It is really hard when they only know one language. Their language really matters.)

Amore, (pseudonym) working with indigenous students, particularly those in the first and second grades, has been challenging mainly due to language barriers. Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners have their own unique languages, which are different from the language the user is familiar with. This language difference becomes a hurdle in the teaching-learning process.

Furthermore, these young learners are more comfortable narrating stories in their native language, which adds to the complexity of the situation. The user, being unfamiliar with the indigenous language, finds it difficult to communicate effectively and understand the students, thus making the teaching process not easy.

“Okay my experiences neophyte teachers teaching indigenous students mainly teaching IP learners is really not kanang not easy because is the main reason is really language barrier kay lahi mn gyud ilang inistoryahan most specially sa ako handling or teaching grade 1 and 2 to the learners bata pa sila mas anad gyud sila na mag storya gamit ilang own language”.(IDI-11)

(In my experience, new teachers teaching indigenous students, especially IP learners, find it is really hard because of the language barrier. They speak a different language, especially for me when teaching grade 1 and 2 students. They are still young and are more used to speaking in their own language.)

Lastly, Alive (pseudonym) challenging due to communication difficulties. The user and the students had different ways of speaking, which led to misunderstandings and made communication difficult. This language barrier was a significant obstacle in the user's initial teaching experience at this school. The students and the user couldn't fully understand each other, which made the teaching process more difficult.

“Base sa akong experiences sa pagtudlo deria, so akong experience first kanang maglisod ko ug communicate sa mga bata because lahi mi ug inistoryahan, dili gyud mi magkasinabot, so mao na akong us aka experience sa akong first sa pagtudlo deria”. (IDI-09)

(Based on my experience teaching here, I had a hard time communicating with the children because we speak different languages. We could not understand each other, and that was one of my first experiences teaching here.)

Struggling to Educate Indigenous Students amidst Language Barriers and Diverse Academic Abilities

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were challenges faced by educators when teaching indigenous students due to language barriers and varied academic abilities. Language barriers arise because indigenous students often speak their own unique languages, which may be different from the language of instruction used in schools. This can make communication difficult, hindering the students' understanding of lessons and the teachers' ability to effectively impart knowledge. Therefore, diverse academic abilities refer to the range of skills and understanding levels among students. Some students might grasp concepts quickly, while others may need more time and support. This diversity can make it difficult for teachers to cater to each student's individual learning needs, especially in a classroom setting where resources and time are limited.

Mr. Smile (pseudonym) face difficulties in teaching these children because their learning capacity is limited, especially when it comes to English subjects. Even in their native Filipino language, these students struggle, indicating that the language barrier is not just limited to English but also extends to their national language. And difficult to deliver lessons effectively because the students struggle to understand even the Bisaya language, which is another local language.

“So, ang difficult here in teaching indigenous people is when it comes to bata na, as what i have said, lisod kaayo siya mag tudlo kanang ang learning sa bata, learning capacity sa bata mismo is mubo lang especially when it comes to english subjects. Naglisod sila sa filipino how much more sa english subjects. So magkabuang na, kami pud mismo nga teacher, Me, as a teacher, kung mag lisod sila ug sabot sa English lisod pud kayo mag deliver kay mag lisod man gani silag sabot sa bisaya, eh Filipino pa nato, how much more if English pa”. (IDI-07)

(The difficult part of teaching indigenous children is, as I mentioned, it is really hard to teach because the children's learning capacity is low, especially in English subjects. They struggle with Filipino, so even more with English. It becomes very challenging for us as teachers. For me, as a teacher, if they find it hard to understand Bisaya, and even Filipino, it is much harder when it comes to English.)

Disciple, (pseudonym) the challenges faced by differing learning paces among students in a classroom. In this particular scenario, out of 28 students, only three are able to keep up with the lessons, while the majority are struggling to grasp the concepts. The teacher is concerned about how to successfully educate and help "low learners" who may require additional time or alternative techniques to comprehend the topic.

“Naay part gyud sir na maglisod kay naay bata na out of 28 students tulo lang gyud sila ang makacatch-up sa lesson tungod sa ilang kaugalingong language moa nang challenges na sa akoa unsaon nako pagdeal sa uban nga sa low learner”. (IDI-08)

(Sir, there are times when it is really difficult because out of 28 students, only three can keep up with the lesson due to their own language. That's my challenge how to deal with the others who are slower learners.)

Lastly, Alive (pseudonyms) they struggle with adjusting to a new teaching environment. In their previous experience at a private school, the students were fast learners, which may have allowed for a quicker pace of instruction. However, in their current position at an Indigenous Peoples (IP) school, they are facing challenges due to language barriers and the slower learning pace of the students. A multi-grade teacher is responsible for educating students from many grade levels in the same classroom. This complicates their task even further because they must cater to multiple learning levels at the same time.

“So, dako kaayu ko ug kaning adjustment because sa private mono lng ko din the learners is very fast learner jud siya to be honest like deria sa IP school so naga adjust jud ko because ang bata is kabalo gyud tah kay sa IP is slow learner din multigrade pa gyud ko, so lisod gyud cya most specially sa akoa kay di pud ko hawod sa ilahang language so I say said adjustment ang akoang for this school year pa gyud na adjustment”. (IDI-09)

(I had to make big adjustments because I used to teach in a private school where the learners were very fast. Here in the IP School, I'm really adjusting because the students are slow learners, and I'm also teaching multi-grade, which makes it harder. It is especially difficult for me because I'm not fluent in their language. So, this school year has been all about adjusting for me.)

Prioritizing Cultural Understanding and Respect for Diverse Learning Styles

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were challenges faced by educators when teaching indigenous students due to cultural differences. Students from varied cultural backgrounds participate in a diversified school setting. Understanding these cultures can help teachers foster a more inclusive and courteous learning environment. Each pupil learns in their own unique way. Some people learn visually, some through auditory means, while some prefer hands-on experiences. Respecting varied learning styles entails recognizing these variations and tailoring teaching techniques accordingly. Therefore, encourage were non-indigenous teachers to be culturally sensitive and adaptive in their teaching methods to cater to the diverse needs of their students.

Melody, (pseudonym) the neophyte expresses a non-indigenous teacher's commitment and dedication to teaching in a culturally diverse context. Despite difficulties of the teacher finds the experience rewarding. They highlights cultural competence, which involves recognizing and appreciating their pupils' many cultural origins. Recognizing that cultural variations can result in diverse learning styles, communication preferences, and educational viewpoints.

“Lisud, usa ka mahagiton, apan makatagbaw, giisip ang akong kaugalingon isip usa ka dili lumad nga magtutudlo gihatag nako ang akong oras pinaagi sa pag-una sa akong katakus sa kultura, nagtinguha nga masabtan ang kultural nga kagikan sa akong mga estudyante nga mahimo’g adunay lainlaing mga istilo sa pagkat-on, gusto sa komunikasyon, ug mga panan-aw sa edukasyon ug aktibong pag-apil sa propesyonal nga kalamboan aron mapalambo ang akong mga gawi sa pagtudlo”. (IDI-14)

(It is difficult and challenging, but fulfilling, I give my time by prioritizing my understanding of their culture. I strive to understand the cultural background of my students, who may have different learning styles, communication preferences, and views on education. I also actively engage in professional development to improve my teaching methods.)

Lover, (pseudonym) imparting to the children revolves around the rich diversity of cultures that exist in our world. It's essential for them to understand that every culture, though different, holds its own unique value and beauty. These differences should not be a source of division, but rather, they should be appreciated and respected. This respect extends not only to the traditions and customs of each culture but also to the individuals who belong to them.

“So, akong ginabuhay ginapasabot jud sa bata nga lahi-lahi jud tah ug culture so dapat magrespetohay jud kasabot lng man pud sila na magrespetohay lng, halimbawa lage na dili ko kasabot or dili sila kasabot gina patranslate jud nko”. (IDI-03)

(What I do is explain to the children that we have different cultures, so we should respect each other. They understand that we need to be respectful. For example, if I don't understand something or if they don't understand, I make sure to translate it.)

Lastly, Great (pseudonym) foster an environment of peace, acceptance, and respect, particularly when interacting with individuals from diverse cultures. This means creating a safe space where everyone feels valued and respected for their unique cultural backgrounds. It's not enough to merely tolerate these differences; we must actively embrace and appreciate them. This involves demonstrating genuine respect and love for all cultures, and maintaining a peaceful demeanor that communicates our openness and acceptance.

“kanang kuan peaceful kanang mafeel nila nga kanang open ka na modawat ka sa ilang culture dili kaau ingon nga dili nimo sila respetuhon kailangan naa gyud diha ang respeto ang paghigugma ug kanang kalinaw ug kanang motudlo bitaw ka na walay bias bitaw. Tudloan nimo ug tarong ang mga bata specially sa mga IP students”. (IDI-12)

(You need to create a peaceful environment where they feel that you are open to accepting their culture and that you respect them. It is important to show respect, love, and peace, and to teach without bias. You should teach the children, especially IP students, properly and fairly.)

Contextualizing Lessons Relevant to the Students Culture and Surroundings

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teacher were contextualizing teachings based on the students' culture and surroundings is the technique of incorporating real-world circumstances, cultural allusions, and the local environment into the educational curriculum. This technique seeks to make learning more relevant and interesting for students by linking new information to their prior knowledge and experiences. It not only improves comprehension and memory of the information, but it also promotes respect and appreciation for one's own culture and environment. It acknowledges the kids' experiences and backgrounds, letting them feel seen and heard in the classroom setting.

Lover, (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of contextualizing lessons in a tangible and experiential way. For instance, if the lesson is about the five senses, specifically taste, it's not enough to simply discuss the concepts of bitter, sweet, and so on. Instead, it's more effective to bring materials that students can interact with directly, such as sugar and salt. This way, students can experience the lesson firsthand, making the learning process more engaging and memorable.

“We need to contextualize halimbawa magpa activity ko ug, unsa gani akong ipa-activity, unsa gani akong gi lesson. katong taste unsa gani to, tung five senses so, ay dili so mga lasa lng to so, pait, a sweet, so nagadala ko ug materials jud dili jud ko nga kani example, dili ko word to word, kong dili contextualize siya nga kanang makita within the, lng jud sa ilang balay. Pariha anang nagadala ko ug asukal kanang ampalaya ingna na mga examples ang imong buhaton”. (IDI-03)

(We need to make lessons relevant to their lives. For example, if I give an activity related to the five senses, like tasting, I do not just use abstract examples. I bring real materials that they can see and use at home. For instance, if we're talking about tastes, I might bring sugar and bitter melon as examples.)

Morina, (pseudonym) the importance of integrating Indigenous Peoples' (IP) culture into the educational curriculum, and how this has been achieved through localization and division-wide implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The integration of IP culture and the adoption of MELCs are intended to promote inclusivity and respect for diversity in the educational system. Using examples from the students' surroundings and culture makes the learning process more interesting and meaningful for them, resulting in a greater understanding of the concepts.

“So when it comes to integration of sa pag integrate sa IP culture as much as possible na nalocalize ang amoang bow ug kanang melcs karon is kumbaga division wide mn siya kumabaga general man siya tanan so pagabot na dria sa classroom setting gina localize namo siya like sa mga example kong unsa rah gyud makita sa palibot”. (IDI-06)

(When it comes to integrating IP culture, we try to make our lessons as localized as possible. Although the curriculum is general and covers everything across the division, we adapt it for our classroom by using examples that are relevant to the students' surroundings.)

Lastly, Amore (pseudonym) the importance integration of indigenous culture into the teaching process through contextualization and localization. This means that when delivering lessons, examples should be drawn from the students' own environment and experiences, particularly those that are relevant to their indigenous culture. By contextualizing the lessons, the teacher makes the content more relatable and easier to understand.

“Integrating indigenous kato siya, mag contextualize mga example nga imong ihatag kuntahay magdeliver ka kanang lesson so ang mga examples nga kanang pwede nimo himoun nga kanang klase nimo contextualize nimo meaning kanang magexample ka kanang Makita or localize na Makita sa ilahang palibot para dali nila masabtan kong unsa tong buot nimo ipasabot”. (IDI-11)

(When integrating indigenous culture, you need to use examples that fit their context. For example, when delivering a lesson, use examples that they can see or find in their own environment. This helps them understand what you are trying to teach more easily.)

Research Question 2: What are the coping strategies of neophyte non- indigenous elementary handling indigenous pupil learners?

This question focused on understanding the strategies, approaches, and coping mechanisms employed by neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers to address the challenges of teaching indigenous students or in IP schools. It explored how these teachers navigate obstacles such as student difficulties, curriculum complexities, instructional dilemmas, classroom management issues, and other related challenges. The question aimed to uncover the various techniques and practices utilized by neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers to overcome these challenges and adapt to the demands of teaching in IP schools effectively. The following themes were: Embracing Flexibility to Understand and Communicate Effectively Within their Language and Culture, Seeking Support from Stakeholders for Guidance and Insights, Conducting Home Visits to Understand IP Students’ Behavior and Circumstances, and Managing Students Behaviors with Guidance from Colleagues.

Embracing Flexibility to Understand and Communicate Effectively Within their Language and Culture

Embracing flexibility to comprehend and communicate effectively within their language and culture is a notion centered on adaptability and openness in cross- cultural communication. This entails being adaptable in our approach to learning and understanding new languages and cultures, as well as adjusting our communication styles for effective interaction. Embracing flexibility in this context involves acknowledging and appreciating cultural difference. It entails being open to new viewpoints and willing to change our own behaviors and attitudes in order to create mutual understanding and respect. Finally, this technique encourages effective communication, more cultural awareness, and pleasant cross-cultural encounters.

Table 3. *Coping Strategies of Neophyte Non-indigenous Elementary Teachers Teaching in IP Schools*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Embracing Flexibility to Understand and Communicate Effectively Within their Language and Culture	This is a real challenge, sir. As a teacher, we need to be flexible and very patient, especially since I handle both grade 1 and 2 students. It's not easy because I teach multiple grades. Some children are very active, some are quiet and understand quickly, and some are very active and still do not understand. IDI-01 I keep an open mind and stay adaptable. This is effective support for indigenous students and helps me handle any challenges I face in teaching. IDI-14 Yes, I do ask questions, especially to my co-teachers, who know more about this. Our school head is indigenous, so they are a big help to us. They provide valuable suggestions and support. IDI-08
Seeking Support from Stakeholders for Guidance and Insights	Yes, of course, when it comes to your teachers, it is important to stay close to your school head. If you could not reach the school head, you should approach your teachers. The school itself should be involved, and the school head should not be the only point of contact. It is better if there are IP (Indigenous Peoples) teachers with you. IDI-03 Yes, I ask for help from my co-teachers, especially those with 7 or 8 years of experience, and from the IP school head who was here before. I also ask my learners what they want and how they feel about things. This is where I get my ideas and guidance. IDI-05 Yes, I do ask questions, especially to my co-teachers because they know a lot. Our school head, who is purely IP or indigenous, is also very helpful. They offer a lot of assistance and suggestions for these kinds of things. IDI- 02
Conducting Home Visits to Understand IP Students’ Behavior and Circumstances	So, we do home visits to get to know the community and understand why the students behave the way they do and how they act in the classroom. IDI-02 My problem with the indigenous students, sir, is that their homes are very far, so they are often absent. What I do is conduct home visits to find out why the student keeps being absent. It is important for teachers to know how many days the child has been absent and why. So, we visit their homes to understand that, the problem is they do not have enough money, food, or allowance, which is why they cannot go to school. These are the common issues I encounter with the students. We do home visits even if their place is far. During MPRA, we schedule visits to their area to understand their situation better. But their community is approachable, so it is okay. IDI-01

We also conduct home visits with indigenous students and their families. This helps us get to know the students better. Sometimes, we have short conversations with the parents to understand the child's situation at home. We also have school activities, like outreach programs, where we join in, and through that, we can engage more with them. IDI-06

Managing Students Behaviors In teaching, students have different behaviors, so it is important to understand their attitudes. In my class, I with Guidance from Colleagues have a SPED student, and I also have a sibling who is mute. We get along because they use sign language, so it is not difficult for me. That mute child is close to my heart because they are well-behaved. There are also other students who are noisy, but that is normal for kids. Of course, sometimes you need to scold them, but I don't really get angry. When I do scold, it is only inside the classroom. IDI-10

Challenges in terms of what kind of challenges, it is not easy because some kids really do not listen to you, but you have to get their attention. You can call their attention or ask them directly to listen, or even use them as an example. IDI-01

Okay, by asking for advice from my co-teachers and by deeply understanding the students' behavior, I also ask my co-teachers since they have been in this field for a long time and know better what needs to be done for the kids. IDI-02

Miss Behave, (pseudonym) the teacher was reflects the challenges and demands of being a multi-grade teacher, particularly for grades 1 and 2, and emphasizes the need for flexibility and patience in this role. Being a multi-grade teacher is a difficult task since it requires managing and educating children from multiple grade levels at the same time. Each grade level has its own learning objectives, and each student learns at their own rate, requiring a great degree of flexibility.

“Kani siya sir is laban jud, dapat as teacher is flexible ta din taas ug patient specially sa akong duha akong gi handilan grade 1 and 2 dli gyud siya dali kay ako multi-grade teacher deria as teacher duha mn akong gidala so taas jud ug patience kay naa man gud bata na moode kaayu din naa pud bata na mo puyo lang unya makasabot, din naa gyud bata na moode kaau na di pa gyud makasabot”. (IDI-01)

(This is a real challenge, sir. As a teacher, we need to be flexible and very patient, especially since I handle both grade 1 and 2 students. It is not easy because I teach multiple grades. Some children are very active, some are quiet and understand quickly, and some are very active and still do not understand.)

Melody, (pseudonym) the teachers was emphasizes the importance of being open-minded and adaptable in effectively supporting indigenous students and overcoming any potential challenges in the teaching process. Being open-minded means being willing to learn and understand the unique cultures, traditions, and perspectives of the indigenous students. This involves acknowledging and respecting their cultural heritage and incorporating it into the teaching process.

“Nagpabilin kong open ang hunahuna ug mapahiangay, kini usa ka epektibo nga suporta sa mga lumad nga estudyante ug pag-handle sa bisan unsang mga hagit nga akong masugatan sa proseso sa pagtudlo”. (IDI-14)

(I keep an open mind and stay adaptable. This is effective support for indigenous students and helps me handle any challenges I face in teaching.)

Disciple, (pseudonym) As a dedicated educator, they find their self frequently seeking the wisdom and insights of my fellow teachers, particularly those who have been in the profession for 7 or 8 years longer than they have. Their experience and knowledge are invaluable resources that enable me to grow and improve in my role. Previously, as the head of an Indigenous Peoples (IP) school, it was tasked with a unique set of challenges and responsibilities. They found that seeking advice and learning from the colleagues was instrumental in successfully navigating these challenges.

“Yes, nagapangyu ko ug tabang sa akong mga co-teachers specially sa katong 7 years, 8 years sa mas ahead pa sa akong kuan katong IP na school head before and of course sa akong mga learners kay nagapagutana kong unsa ilang gusto na ingani bah?, deria ko nagakuan”. (IDI- 05)

(Yes, I ask for help from my co-teachers, especially those who have been teaching for 7 or 8 years and are more experienced than I am, like the IP school head before. I also ask my learners what they want, to find out how they prefer things to be done. That is where I get my guidance.)

Lastly, Talker (pseudonym) they was realize the immense value in seeking guidance and support from those around them. This is particularly true for my fellow teachers who have been in the profession for 7 or 8 years longer than me. Their wealth of experience and knowledge has been a tremendous resource that has greatly enriched my own teaching practice. For those previous role as the head of an Indigenous Peoples (IP) school, it was deeply aware of the unique challenges and responsibilities that came with the position. They found that my colleagues, especially my school head who is a pure IP or native, had a profound understanding of these challenges and were able to provide invaluable advice and assistance.

“Oo, naga pangutana gyud ko, labaw na gyud sa akong co-teachers sila jud ang nakabalo specially sa akong school head since among school head diri kay pure IP or pure lumad sila sir siya makatabang so siya dako kaayong tabang sa amoa in terms na ingana nga mga butang, nga naa siyay mga suggestion”. (IDI-02)

(Yes, I do ask questions, especially to my co- teachers, who know more about this. Our school head is indigenous, so they are a big help to us. They provide valuable suggestions and support.)

Seeking Support from Stakeholders for Guidance and Insights

Seeking support from stakeholders for guidance and insights is essential for making informed decisions and achieving organizational goals. Engaging with stakeholders such as customers, employees, partners, and community members provides a diverse range of perspectives and expertise that can illuminate potential opportunities and risks. This collaborative approach not only enhances the quality of decision-making but also fosters a sense of ownership and alignment among stakeholders. By actively soliciting and integrating their feedback, organizations can better navigate complex challenges, adapt to changing conditions, and drive more effective and sustainable outcomes.

Talker, (pseudonym) a well-rounded support system in schools is crucial, involving both close collaboration with the school head and direct engagement with teachers. This approach prevents administrative barriers from hindering support and communication. Including the entire school community and having Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers ensures cultural relevance and a more inclusive environment, enhancing the educational experience and effectively addressing the needs of IP students.

Oo yes, of course sa akong teachers sa akong school head so dapat doul jud ka sa imong school head, kong dili kaya sa school head didtoa na jud ka sa mga teachers mo approach man pud ang school dili pud dinha unya dli pud IP ang school head, sa IP teacher jud. So nindot jud ug naa tay kauban na IP na teachers.(IDI-03)

(Yes, of course, when it comes to your teachers, it is important to stay close to your school head. If you could not reach the school head, you should approach your teachers. The school itself should be involved, and the school head should not be the only point of contact. It is better if there are IP (Indigenous Peoples) teachers with you.)

Mr. Chinito, (pseudonym) collaborative approach to seeking guidance in education by consulting experienced co-teachers, engaging with the culturally knowledgeable IP school head, and involving learners. This inclusive strategy combines diverse insights and student feedback to create a well-rounded, responsive, and effective educational environment

“Yes, nagapangyu ko ug tabang sa akong mga co-teachers specially sa katong 7 years, 8 years sa mas ahead pa sa akoa kuan katong IP na school head before and of course sa akong mga learners kay nagapagutana kong unsa ilang gusto na ingani bah?, deria ko nagakuan”.(IDI-05)

(Yes, I ask for help from my co-teachers, especially those with 7 or 8 years of experience, and from the IP school head who was here before. I also ask my learners what they want and how they feel about things. This is where I get my ideas and guidance.)

Talker, (pseudonym) Using the knowledge of experienced co-teachers and the Indigenous school head is very valuable. Experienced teachers offer practical advice, while the Indigenous school head provides important cultural insights and suggestions. Combining these perspectives helps solve problems effectively and improves the overall educational experience

“Oo, naga pangutana gyud ko, labaw na gyud sa akong co-teachers sila jud ang nakabalo specially sa akong school head since among school head diri kay pure IP or pure lumad sila sir siya makatabang so siya dako kaayong tabang sa amoa in terms na ingana nga mga butang, nga naa siyay mga suggestion”.(IDI-02)

(Yes, I do ask questions, especially to my co- teachers because they know a lot. Our school head, who is purely IP or indigenous, is also very helpful. They offer a lot of assistance and suggestions for these kinds of things.)

Conducting Home Visits to Understand IP Students' Behavior and Circumstances

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were conducting house visits to understand IP (Intellectual Property) students' behavior and circumstances entails taking a holistic approach to learning about the students' living arrangements, family dynamics, and personal issues. The theory is based on the belief that a student's home environment has a substantial impact on academic performance and conduct. Educators and school administrators can better understand the problems that these students encounter by visiting their homes, such as resource limits, household duties, or other circumstances that may influence their participation in intellectual property studies. This comprehensive information can then be used to create specific educational techniques and support systems to help these children succeed. Home visits also allow the school and families to strengthen their relationships, providing a collaborative environment that improves students' overall development.

Talker, (pseudonym) conducting home visitation is a method of community engagement that allows us to interact directly with individuals in their own environment. This strategy provides a unique perspective on the behaviors, attitudes, and conditions that may not be evident in public or communal spaces. By conducting these visits, we gain a deeper understanding of the community members' lives, their daily routines, and the challenges they face.

“So, kami diri nagaconduct ug home visitation para makahalobilo sa community para mahibal- an kong unsa ang nganong ingon ana ilang behavior ug ingana sila sa sulod sa room”.(IDI- 02)

(So, we do home visits to get to know the community and understand why the students behave the way they do and how they act in the classroom.)

Miss Behave, (pseudonym), Home visits are key to understanding and addressing issues in Indigenous communities, especially in remote areas. We've noticed that many children often miss school, and by visiting their homes, we can see why. This helps us understand problems like financial issues, lack of basic needs, and long distances to school. These visits also help us build strong relationships with families and ensure we have enough time to talk and understand their needs, making the communities more open to discussing their challenges.

"Ang akong problema sir sa mga indigenous kay layo gyud ilang mga balay, mao nga permi sila mag-absent. Ang akong ginabuhay ana kay mag-home visit ko para mahibal-an ngano sige ug absent ang bata. Importante nga kabalo ang mga teachers kung pila na ka adlaw nga absent ang bata ug ngano. Mao nga mag-home visit mi para masabtan namo nga, ah, mao diay ang problema kay wala silay budget, wala silay baon, o wala silay bugas mao nga dili maka-eskwela. Kasagaran nga mga problema nga ma- encounter nako sa mga bata kay ingon ana. Nag-home visit mi bisan layo ilang lugar. Sa MPRA, naghatag gyud mi ug schedule aron makaadto mi sa ilang lugar ug mahibal-an ang ilang kahimtang. Pero okay ra pud ang ilang community kay approachable man sila." (IDI-01)

(My problem with the indigenous students, sir, is that their homes are very far, so they are often absent. What I do is conduct home visits to find out why the student keeps being absent. It is important for teachers to know how many days the child has been absent and why. So, we visit their homes to understand that, the problem is they do not have enough money, food, or allowance, which is why they cannot go to school. These are the common issues I encounter with the students. We do home visits even if their place is far. During MPRA, we schedule visits to their area to understand their situation better. But their community is approachable, so it is okay.)

Lastly, Morina (pseudonym) they was revolves around a comprehensive approach to understanding and supporting indigenous students. This involves conducting home visits to these students and their families. The purpose of such visits is to gain a deeper understanding of the student's living conditions, family dynamics, and overall home environment. These visits often include short conversations with the parents to gain insights into the child's status both at home and at school. In addition to home visits, there are also school activities designed to serve as outreach programs. These activities was often joined by colleagues and other members of the educational community. The intention behind these collaborative efforts is to immerse ourselves in the students' cultural and social contexts. By doing so, we can better understand their unique challenges and strengths, which in turn helps us to provide more effective and culturally sensitive support.

"Indigenous students and their families naa pud mi naga conduct na kanang home visitation kana, mas maila-ila jud ang studyante sometimes ahh short converse with their parent lng pud as to kanag unsay status sa bata kong unsa sila dinhi sa ilang panimalay din sa to sa parent usahay naa pud mi kanang school activities kanang like kanang nag silbi siya na outreach mga kauban na apil pud mi through that maka kuan pud mi ma emerge".(IDI-06)

(We also conduct home visits with indigenous students and their families. This helps us get to know the students better. Sometimes, we have short conversations with the parents to understand the children situation at home. We also have school activities, like outreach programs, where we join in, and through that, we can engage more with them.)

Managing Students Behaviors with Guidance from Colleagues

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were managing student behaviors with guidance from colleagues emphasizes the importance of collaboration and shared expertise in educational settings. It recognizes that each student is unique, and their behaviors can be influenced by a multitude of factors that may not always be apparent or understood by a single educator. This strategy requires educators to collaborate, combining their expertise, experiences, and views in order to better understand and manage student behaviors. They may discuss specific instances, give information about students' origins or personal situations, or devise techniques for dealing with specific behavioral concerns. This collaborative technique enables a more thorough and nuanced knowledge of student behavior. It also encourages the development of more effective and targeted intervention options. Educators can better traverse the difficulties of student behavior management by drawing on their colleagues' collective wisdom, resulting in a more conducive learning environment for all students.

Cutie, (pseudonym) teaching requires understanding the different behaviors and needs of students. In my classroom, I've worked with various personalities and learning abilities, including students with Special Education needs who show great potential. One student who is mute communicates in his own way, which has become a valuable part of our classroom. Despite some noisy and disruptive behavior from other students, I stay patient and calm, as these challenges are part of the learning environment.

"Sa pagtudlo, lahi-lahi og batasan ang mga estudyante, mao nang kinahanglan sabton gyud unsa ilang kinaiya. Sa akong klase, naa ko'y SPED nga estudyante, ug naa pud koy mute nga igsuon. Magkasinabot ra mi kay mag-sign language ra siya, mao nga dili lisod para nako. Kato nga mute nga bata, duol pud sa akong kasingkasing kay buotan man. Naa pud uban estudyante nga saba, pero normal ra na sa mga bata. Syempre, kinahanglan mangasaba ka usahay, pero dili ko maglagot gyud. Ang akong pagsaba, sa sulod ra sa classroom taman."(IDI-10)

(In teaching, students have different behaviors, so it is important to understand their attitudes. In my class, I have a SPED student, and

I also have a sibling who is mute. We get along because they use sign language, so it is not difficult for me. That mute child is close to my heart because they are well-behaved. There are also other students who are noisy, but that is normal for kids. Of course, sometimes you need to scold them, but I do not really get angry. When I do scold, it is only inside the classroom.)

Miss Behave, (pseudonym) teaching has a variety of problems, especially when working with pupils who struggle to pay attention or follow directions. These problems are not insurmountable, but they do necessitate a distinct strategy and a lot of patience. One of the primary challenges is capturing and maintaining the student's attention. This is especially true for those who are easily distracted or have difficulty focusing. As a teacher, it is essential to find creative and effective ways to engage these students.

”Challenges in terms of unsa na challenges, dili pud siya dali si kay kay lahi jud ang kuan sa bata na di jud maminaw sa imuha pero dapat kuhaon gyud nimo ang iyahang attention. Or call the attention or kanang imuhang siyang tawagon para maminaw or himoun nmo siya nga example”. (IDI-01)

(Challenges in terms of what kind of challenges, it is not easy because some kids really did not listen to you, but you have to get their attention. You can call their attention or ask them directly to listen, or even use them as an example.)

Lastly, Talker (pseudonym) navigating the complexity of teaching can be challenging, especially when dealing with a wide range of student behaviors. However, one of the most useful ways were discovered is to seek advice from my more experienced co-teachers. Their extensive expertise, obtained through years of field experience, is an invaluable resource for understanding and managing various behaviors.

“Okay, by seeking advises my co-teachers and by understanding deeply their behavior ug nagapangutana ko sa akua co-teachers since sila ang dugay ani nga field. Ug mas nakabalo sa mga dapat pang buhaton sa mga bata”. (IDI-02)

(Okay, by asking for advice from my co-teachers and by deeply understanding the students' behavior, I also ask my co-teachers since they have been in this field for a long time and know better what needs to be done for the kids.)

Research Question 3: What are the insights can neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers share the academe?

This question delved into the unique perspectives, observations, and understandings gained by neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were teaching indigenous students or In IP schools. It sought to uncover the valuable insights, reflections, and lessons learned by neophyte non-indigenous teachers through their experiences in the classroom. The question aimed to capture their evolving understanding of pedagogy, content knowledge, student learning, instructional strategies, and other aspects related to teaching in IP schools. By exploring these insights, the research aimed to contribute to the broader knowledge base and inform professional development initiatives for neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers. The following themes were: Effectives Instruction Results in Positives Students' Performance, Emphasize Technology's Vital Pole in Education for Improved learning and Digital Literacy, Offer Teachers Training on Culturally Responsive Teaching for Indigenous Students, and Teaching Indigenous Students Requires Cultural Understanding and Adaptability

Effectives Instruction Results in Positives Students' Performance

Effective instruction involves clear communication of concepts, engaging teaching methods, and a well-structured curriculum that caters to the diverse learning needs of students. It requires teachers to be knowledgeable in their subject matter, skilled in various teaching strategies, and capable of creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment. When instruction is effective, students are more likely to grasp the concepts being taught, stay engaged in the learning process, and develop critical thinking skills. This not only leads to improved academic performance but also fosters a love for learning. Furthermore, effective instruction also includes regular assessment and feedback, which help track students' progress and identify areas for improvement. By addressing these areas and tailoring instruction to meet individual learning needs, students' performance can be significantly enhanced.

Miss Behave, (pseudonym) the neophyte non-indigenous teacher emphasizes the influential role of a teacher's performance in shaping the learning outcomes of their students. As educators, the quality of our teaching directly impacts the comprehension and academic progress of our students. If we perform our duties effectively, employing clear communication, engaging teaching methods, and a deep understanding of the subject matter, it facilitates easier understanding for the students. Since, the measure of our performance as teachers is reflected in our students' understanding of the lessons and their academic progress.

Table 4. Insights of Neophyte Non-indigenous Elementary Teachers Teaching in IP Schools

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Effectives Instruction Results in Positives Students' Performance	As a teacher, your good performance is reflected in the outcomes seen in your students. If you perform well, the students will understand better, and it becomes easier for them to grasp concepts. A teacher should always strive to use the simplest methods to ensure that the students can easily understand and retain the information. IDI-01 The importance of having good performance as a teacher is that it will reflect in your students. If you are a diligent teacher, your students will also be diligent and this will reflect in their performance. If you are effective in teaching, then the learning of the students will also be effective. IDI- 05 For me, it is important to know how we are doing because it also shows in the students. If you don't teach

	properly, the students won't learn well. But if you teach well, you'll definitely see the students learning effectively. IDI-07
Emphasize Technology's Vital Pole in Education for Improved learning and Digital Literacy	I really want to use technology here, even just a TV, to show them things, even if it is a recording or something downloaded. I want them to see examples of how things work, like in experiments. It is better for them to see something rather than just imagine it, so it would be really helpful. IDI-04 They need to learn computer skills and new technologies. That's one of the challenges for IP learners because we have very little technology here only one laptop for many students. It would be good if they at least learned the basics, like typing in Microsoft programs, so they wouldn't struggle as much in the future. That is what I want to improve, sir. IDI-08 To improve our quality of education, we really need more technology. If we teach students without any technology, they will not learn well. It is much better if they can see things. They need to know how to use computers because it is difficult for them otherwise. They might know about Facebook, but they do not know how to do research. Technology is really important. IDI-09
Offer Teachers Training on Culturally Responsive Teaching For Indigenous Students	There should be more seminars and training for teachers to learn more. Is there anything else teachers can do? More training or workshops could help teachers with this. IDI-01 Teachers should attend seminars and training to learn how to handle IP students better. IDI-13 Provide training for teachers on culturally responsive teaching methods, including strategies to include indigenous perspectives in their lessons. This could involve workshops, seminars, or ongoing professional development programs. IDI-14
Teaching Indigenous Students Requires Cultural Understanding and Adaptability	I just suggest that if they are assigned to an IP (Indigenous Peoples) community, they should really research the background of the community so they can have cultural awareness. They need to understand how far the place is and always be prepared for that distance. Also, they should be culturally aware of the specific indigenous group, as each IP community is unique with its own practices and traditions. IDI-06 When you are in an IP community, you should first learn their culture. You need to be aware that what you say might affect them since their customs could be different from what you are used to. You should also get to know your students because life in the mountains is different from life in the lowlands. Understand their behavior and their families, and build good relationships with them. If you're in a school setting, make sure to ask for permission from the community, show respect, and identify who the leaders are. IDI-09 When teaching Indigenous students, it is important to understand their cultural background, unique challenges, and learning styles so that we can be effective and wise educators. IDI-14

"As teachers akong good performance as teachers, so makit-an pud nimo ang kinalabasan sa imong performance sa imong studyante so kong goods performance ka so makasabot gyud ang bata so dali lng gyud makasabot so s teacher is buhaton gyud niya ang pinakasayun nga buhatan aron nga mas masabtan sa bata kong unsay kaya na buhaton na pinakasayun gyud para masulod gyud sa huna-huna sa bata bah". (IDI-01)

(As a teacher, your good performance is reflected in the outcomes seen in your students. If you perform well, the students will understand better, and it becomes easier for them to grasp concepts. A teacher should always strive to use the simplest methods to ensure that the students can easily understand and retain the information.)

Mr. Chinito, (pseudonym) the performance of a teacher is crucial as it has a direct impact on the learning outcomes of students. When a teacher is effective in their teaching methods, it creates a positive learning environment that motivates students to engage, learn, and perform better. A teacher's good performance is reflected not just in their ability to impart knowledge, but also in their capacity to inspire, motivate, and understand their students' unique needs. This effectiveness in teaching transforms into effective learning for the students.

"Okay, the importance of having good performance of course magreflect pud imong students sa imuha if gahot ka na teacher of course imong mga students mang-gahot pud magreflect pud sila sa imuha, kong okay ka mag kuan magtudlo, kong effective ka si effective pud ang learning sa bata". (IDI-05)

(The importance of having good performance as a teacher is that it will reflect in your students. If you are a diligent teacher, your students will also be diligent and this will reflect in their performance. If you are effective in teaching, then the learning of the students will also be effective.)

Lastly, Mr. Smile (pseudonym) the neophyte non-indigenous teacher were understanding one's performance as a teacher is indeed crucial, as it directly impacts the students' learning experience. If a teacher excels in their teaching methods, it is likely to be reflected in the students' knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. If a teacher is effective in their instruction, it naturally enhances the students' comprehension and retention of the material. This is because effective teaching methods cater to the students' unique learning styles, fostering a more engaging and productive learning environment.

"So for me, it is important makabalo tah sa atong performance because it is also reflect sa mga bata kong wla ka nagtinarog ug tudlo dira unsa man mahibaw-an sa bata, kong nagtironing ka ug tudlo deria syimpre ang learning sa bata naa gyud makita gyud". (IDI-07)

(For me, it is important to know how we're doing because it also shows in the students. If you do not teach properly, the students will not learn well. But if you teach well, you'll definitely see the students learning effectively.)

Emphasize Technology's Vital Pole in Education for Improved learning and Digital Literacy

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were technology plays a pivotal role in modern education, significantly enhancing learning outcomes and promoting digital literacy. The integration of technology in education provides an array of benefits that cater to the diverse needs of learners in the 21st century. Technology facilitates improved learning by making education more engaging and interactive. Digital tools and resources such as educational apps, interactive whiteboards, and e-books make learning more dynamic and interesting. They enable students to visualize complex concepts, thus improving comprehension and retention. The use of technology in education promotes digital literacy, a crucial skill in today's digital age. By using technology in the classroom, students learn how to navigate the digital world responsibly and effectively. They acquire skills such as online research, digital communication, and cyber safety, which are essential for their future careers and personal growth.

Madasig, (pseudonym) It appears that you are referring to advanced technology, such as a highly advanced television or display system, that can take downloaded records and present them in a way that significantly improves knowledge and comprehension. This technology has the potential to change the way we consume video, creating an extremely immersive and participatory experience. Instead of simply staring at a two-dimensional screen, viewers might interact with the content, almost as if they were part of it. For example, if you're conducting an experiment or presenting a complex concept, this technology could allow viewers to see and understand it in a way that surpasses their imagination. They could see every detail, every nuance, and every aspect of the experiment or concept, making it much easier for them to understand.

“Gusto gyud nako diri kanang maski, kanang technology bisan lang untag TV nga mapakita bahalag record bahalag downloaded, mapakita nako sa ilaha nga ingon ani, ingon ani. Parihas anang mag experiment gusto unta nko naa silay Makita ana lang. Dili kaau sila kasabot ug mag imagine lang sila mas maayu na naa silay Makita so maski papano.(IDI-04)

(I really want to use technology here, even just a TV, to show them things, even if it is a recording or something downloaded. I want them to see examples of how things work, like in experiments. It is better for them to see something rather than just imagine it, so it would be really helpful.)

Disciple, (pseudonym) It suggests that you are concerned about a lack of access to technology, notably computers, in some learning situations, possibly in disadvantaged or rural communities. They stating that to understand and learn about computers, one needs to have access to a computer. This is particularly crucial because computer literacy is becoming increasingly important in our technology driven world.

Without access to such technology, learners, particularly those in IP (Indigenous Peoples) communities, risk falling behind in their education and future opportunities. This is due to the digital divide, the gap between those who have ready access to computers and the Internet, and those who do not. That there is only one laptop available for many children, which further compounds the issue. However, you also express a hope that even with limited resources, the learners can gradually acquire basic computer skills, such as typing and using applications like Microsoft Word.

“Computer need nila makabalo ug computer kanang, computer skills nga mga new technologies, moa pud na ang isa sa behind ang IP learners, kay gamay rah gyud mi ug technology diri isa rah ka laptop din daghan mga bata nindot mn pud to at least hinay-hinay kabalo silag mga basic lang words na magtypes sila sa Microsoft at least dili na sila ma kuan sa pag-abot sa ubos so mao na akong ika-kuan sir. (IDI-08)

(They need to learn computer skills and new technologies. That is one of the challenges for IP learners because we have very little technology here only one laptop for many students. It would be good if they at least learned the basics, like typing in Microsoft programs, so they would not struggle as much in the future. That is what I want to improve, sir.)

Alive, (pseudonym) the teachers was their emphasizing the crucial role of technology in enhancing the quality of education. Without access to technology, you're suggesting that it becomes challenging to effectively teach and engage students. They were highlighting that while some students may be familiar with certain aspects of technology like social media (Facebook, for example), they lack knowledge in other vital areas such as conducting online research. This could be due to a lack of resources or exposure. They were said that "it's better if they have seen" could be referring to the benefits of visual learning which can be greatly enhanced with the use of technology. Computers and other tech tools can provide visual aids, interactive experiences, and access to a wealth of information that can significantly enrich the learning process.

“Para ma improve among quality of education deria dapat kulang gyud mi ug technology, kong magtudlo mi ug mga bata kong wala gyud technology di gyud sila makabalo mo storya mas nindot kong naa silay Makita. Unsa pa mga computer dapat makabalo na sila kay malisod namn na sila. Kay wala nm sila unsa nay, kaila nm sila ug facebook pero kanang mag research- reseach wah gyud na sila kabal, importanted gyud ang technology”.(IDI-09)

(To improve our quality of education, we really need more technology. If we teach students without any technology, they will not learn well. It is much better if they can see things. They need to know how to use computers because it is difficult for them otherwise. They might know about Facebook, but they don't know how to do research. Technology is really important.)

Offer Teachers Training on Culturally Responsive Teaching for Indigenous Students

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were offering teacher training on culturally responsive teaching for indigenous students revolves around enhancing the educational experience by acknowledging, respecting, and incorporating the cultural heritage of these students into the teaching process. This approach recognizes that traditional teaching methods often do not cater to the unique cultural contexts of Indigenous students, which can lead to disengagement and lower academic performance. Culturally responsive teaching seeks to bridge this gap by equipping teachers with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to create an inclusive and effective learning environment. This training would provide educators with an understanding of Indigenous cultures, histories, and contemporary issues, allowing them to integrate this knowledge into their curriculum and teaching practices.

Miss Behave, (pseudonym) was emphasizes the need for continuous professional development for teachers through seminars, trainings, and workshops. This implies that these educational opportunities give intellectual sustenance for educators, allowing them to grow and improve in their careers.

“Kani siya is that more seminars, more trainings para mas makuan sa teachers nga. naa pa diay mabuhat laing sa teachers? Or training or other workshop na buhaton ni teacher ani so that’s it”. (IDI-01)

(There should be more seminars and training for teachers to learn more. Is there anything else teachers can do? More training or workshops could help teachers with this.)

Mr. Gwapo, (pseudonym) the teacher was effort to enhance the educational experience of Indigenous Peoples (IP) pupils, a series of seminars and trainings will be organized for teachers. These professional development activities aim to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively handle and teach IP pupils. The seminars will cover a range of topics including understanding the unique cultural backgrounds, learning styles, and challenges faced by IP pupils.

“Ang mga teacher’s mopailawom sa pahitaboon sa mga seminar ug pagbansay-bansay kon unsaon pagdumala sa mga IP pupils”. (IDI-13)

(Teachers should attend seminars and training to learn how to handle IP students better.)

Melody, (pseudonym) the neophyte non-indigenous teacher were provide teachers with training on culturally responsive teaching practices, particularly those that incorporate indigenous perspectives. This training could take the form of workshops, seminars, or ongoing professional development programs. The goal is to equip educators with the knowledge and skills to understand, respect, and integrate the cultural heritage, history, and perspectives of indigenous students into their lessons. This approach not only enriches the learning experience for all students but also helps indigenous students feel seen, valued, and engaged.

”Paghatag og pagbansay alang sa mga magtutudlo sa culturally responsive nga mga pamaagi sa pagtudlo, lakip ang mga strategy sa pag-apil sa lumad nga mga panglantaw sa ilang mga lessons. Mahimong maglakip kini sa mga workshop, seminar, o nagpadayon nga propesyonal nga mga programa sa pagpalambo”. (IDI-14)

(Provide training for teachers on culturally responsive teaching methods, including strategies to include indigenous perspectives in their lessons. This could involve workshops, seminars, or ongoing professional development programs.)

Teaching Indigenous Students Requires Cultural Understanding and Adaptability

The neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers were teaching Indigenous students effectively requires a deep understanding of their unique cultural backgrounds and an ability to adapt teaching methods accordingly. Indigenous cultures often have distinct traditions, values, and ways of understanding the world, which can significantly influence how students learn. Therefore, educators need to be aware of these cultural differences and be flexible in their teaching approaches. This might involve incorporating Indigenous knowledge and perspectives into the curriculum, using culturally relevant teaching materials, or employing teaching strategies that respect and value Indigenous ways of learning. By doing so, educators can create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment for Indigenous students, promoting their academic success and personal growth.

Morina, (pseudonym) the neophyte non-indigenous teacher were suggests that teachers assigned to Indigenous Peoples (IP) communities should first conduct research to gain a deeper understanding of the specific cultural background of the community they will be working with. This cultural awareness is crucial because each IP community is unique, with its own traditions, values, and ways of learning. By gaining this understanding, teachers can tailor their teaching methods and curriculum to be more culturally relevant and respectful. Additionally, this awareness can help teachers build stronger relationships with their students and the broader community, fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment. This approach emphasizes the importance of respecting and valifying the diversity within and among IP communities in the educational process.

“So, akong ma suggest lng gyud sir, is kuntahay ma assign sila sa IP community is eh research jud nila unsay background para naa silay cultural awareness pasubida nila kuanon pa gyud nila kong unsa kalayo ang lugar pangandaman gyud permi kanang kalay-on syimpre pangandaman permi, and then ano lng pud. maging cultura aware lng pud sila nga kanang kong unsa na nga indigenous kay I believe nmn pud na every IP community lahi-lahi pa gyud na sila kanang mga unsay twag ana kumabaga notion ang practices”.(IDI-

06)

(I just suggest that if they are assigned to an IP (Indigenous Peoples) community, they should really research the background of the community so they can have cultural awareness. They need to understand how far the place is and always be prepared for that distance. Also, they should be culturally aware of the specific indigenous group, as each IP community is unique with its own practices and traditions.)

Alive, (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of cultural immersion and understanding when teaching in Indigenous Peoples (IP) communities. Before starting, teachers should learn about the local culture to avoid unintentionally offending the community with their words or actions. Recognizing the differences between communities, such as those in the mountains versus those in the lowlands, is crucial. Understanding the behaviors, family structures, and customs of the students is key to building strong relationships. When in school, teachers should also engage with the wider community, showing respect for their practices and acknowledging the authority of community leaders. This approach ensures a respectful and effective educational experience that values the unique cultural context of the students.

“Una kong naa ka sa IP ka mabutang so dapat eh learn ilang culture una-una gyud ang culture sa mga ta okay wala tah kabalo masakitan diay sila sa imong gisulti unya lahi na diay para sa ilaha dapat makablo gyud ka, unya ila-ilahon nimo imong mga stuydante kay lahi rah gyud sa bukid ug sa ubos. Makabalo gyud ka sa ilang batasan ug sa ilang pamilya magbuild ka ug relation sa ilaha. Kong naa ka sa skwelahan so dapat mananghid gyud ka sa community kay ingna para makoan pud bah, magrespect gyud ka, ug kinsay leader sa ilang community”. (IDI-09)

(When you are in an IP community, you should first learn their culture. You need to be aware that what you say might affect them since their customs could be different from what you are used to. You should also get to know your students because life in the mountains is different from life in the lowlands. Understand their behavior and their families, and build good relationships with them. If you are in a school setting, make sure to ask for permission from the community, show respect, and identify who the leaders are.)

Melody, (pseudonym) the teacher were teaching indigenous students indeed requires a deep understanding of their cultural backgrounds, unique challenges, and learning styles. These students often come from rich cultural traditions that shape their worldview and approach to learning. Understanding these aspects allows teachers to tailor their teaching methods and materials to better engage these students. Additionally, indigenous students may face unique challenges such as language barriers or cultural misunderstandings that need to be addressed with sensitivity and respect. Teachers need to be creative and resourceful in finding ways to overcome these challenges, such as incorporating cultural elements into lessons or using teaching strategies that align with indigenous ways of learning. By doing so, they can provide a more inclusive and effective learning experience for indigenous students.

“Sa pagtudlo sa indigenous students kinahalanglan gyud na makasabot tah sa ilang mga culture background, talagsaon nga mga ha git, ug mga style sa pagkat-on, busa mahimong mamugnaon ug maalamon”. (IDI-14)

(When teaching Indigenous students, it is important to understand their cultural background, unique challenges, and learning styles so that we can be effective and wise educators.)

Conclusions

The results of this phenomenological study provided an opportunity to explore and comprehend the real-life experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and valuable insights of neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers. With this gathered information, it was crucial to consider the implications it holds for enhancing the teaching experiences and meeting the specific needs of the neophyte non-indigenous teachers as they progress in their teaching indigenous student’s journey.

The revelation that neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers experience challenges in battling initial changes carried significant meaning. It suggested that these teachers may encounter difficulties in adjusting to the demands and expectations of their new role. The implications of this finding included the need for targeted support, mentorship, and professional development programs that address the specific needs and challenges faced by neophyte non-indigenous teachers. By providing the necessary resources and guidance, educational institutions can better equip these teachers to navigate the initial changes they face and improve their effectiveness in the classroom, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching in IP education.

Moreover, neophyte non-indigenous teachers may use the coping strategies shared by the participants including having a lifelong learner mindset, assessing IP’s students’ learning differences, employing various teaching styles, utilizing different approaches in lesson presentation, and seeking assistance and mentorship, can greatly benefit their professional development. These strategies may enable teachers to continuously grow, personalize instruction, and engage students, and access valuable support and guidance. Implementing these coping mechanisms equips neophyte non-indigenous elementary teachers with the skills and mindset necessary for effective teaching and creating a positive learning environment.

Additionally, the findings that emphasized the importance of continuous learning for neophyte non-indigenous teachers has significant implications for IP schools community. It means that these schools need to prioritize and facilitate opportunities for ongoing professional development for their non-indigenous teachers. By recognizing the value of continuous learning, private schools can

ensure that their neophyte non-indigenous teachers stay updated with the latest research, teaching methodologies, and teaching strategies in IP schools community. This commitment to continuous learning enhances the quality of instruction, promotes teacher growth, and ultimately leads to improved student outcomes. It also highlights the need for IP schools to allocate resources and support a culture of learning that empowers teachers to develop and refine their skills throughout their careers. By embracing the importance of continuous learning, private schools in the Davao region may foster an environment of excellence and contribute to the overall advancement of mathematics education in their institutions.

Lastly, for future researchers interested in studying the lived experiences of neophyte non-indigenous teachers in teaching in IP schools this study may provide valuable assistance in gathering necessary information for their own research. The findings, review of related literature, and methodology employed in this study may serve as important references for their research papers.

This study included a sample of ten participants who were actively teaching in IP schools in public schools for six months and minimum of one year services. It is important to note that the selection of participants was restricted to this specific context, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other settings. Limiting the study to only 14 participants may restrict the generalizability of the findings and hinder the comprehensive understanding of neophyte non-indigenous teachers' experiences. The small sample size may not adequately represent the diversity and variability among neophyte non-indigenous teachers, potentially missing out on important insights and nuances. The findings may lack depth and statistical power, impacting the overall robustness of the study. It is crucial to consider these limitations when interpreting the findings and to recognize the need for larger sample sizes in future research to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

This research used a phenomenological approach where the researcher uncovered the essential structures and underlying themes that characterize the phenomenon under study. The researcher recommended that future studies may use a narrative research approach in conducting the study on neophyte non-indigenous teachers because it were focus on understanding individuals' stories, experiences, and perspectives through the lens of storytelling. By capturing the personal narratives of neophyte non-indigenous teachers, this approach may allow for a rich exploration of their unique journeys, challenges, and growth as educators. It may also provide an opportunity to uncover the contextual factors, emotions, and meaning-making processes that shape their teaching experiences. The use of narrative research enables a deeper understanding of the complexities and nuances of neophyte non-indigenous teaching, providing valuable insights for educational practice, teacher training programs, and policy development. It also facilitates the amplification of teachers' voices and promotes a more holistic and empathetic understanding of their professional development.

Lastly, a potential avenue for future research is to conduct a comprehensive needs analysis to explore the specific needs and challenges faced by neophyte non-indigenous teachers during their teaching in indigenous students the IP schools community. This in-depth investigation could identify critical areas where support and training are most necessary to enhance their professional growth and teaching effectiveness. Additionally, studying the impact of tailored interventions based on the needs analysis could offer valuable insights for designing targeted professional development programs and induction procedures that create a positive and supportive environment for neophyte mathematics teachers. By gaining a deeper understanding of their experiences and addressing their individual needs, this research has the potential to better prepare and empower neophyte non-indigenous teachers, ultimately leading to improved mathematics education and student outcomes.

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